

Analysis of a Symmetric 15-Level Multilevel Inverter with Polarity Generation Unit

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Abstract- This paper presents a symmetric 15-level multilevel inverter (MLI) topology designed to achieve enhanced voltage level generation with a reduced number of power electronic components. The proposed configuration is systematically divided into a level synthesis unit and a polarity reversal unit (H-bridge), enabling efficient voltage step formation and full AC output generation. The topology employs twelve power switches, including bidirectional switches in the level generation stage, which facilitate flexible current conduction and proper voltage insertion. Operating in symmetric mode with equal DC voltage sources, the inverter generates fifteen distinct voltage levels, including zero, by selectively inserting or bypassing the DC sources through appropriate switching combination. A Carrier-Based Sinusoidal Pulse Width Modulation (CB- PWM) technique is utilized to regulate the switching operation and enhance output waveform quality. The performance of the proposed topology is validated through simulation analysis under RL load conditions. The results demonstrate that the inverter produces a high-quality staircase output waveform with reduced total harmonic distortion (THD), improved voltage utilization, and efficient device operation.

Keywords: Multilevel inverter (MLI), Symmetric inverter topology, 15-level inverter, Level synthesis unit, H-bridge inverter, Bidirectional switches.

I. INTRODUCTION

Multilevel inverters (MLIs) are highly valued in the field of power electronics due to their wide range of applications and distinct advantages [1–3]. As energy demands continue to rise, integrating MLIs with other power electronic systems has become increasingly important [4]. These inverters are commonly used in variable-frequency drives, electric vehicles, and high-voltage DC transmission systems [5–7]. They are also essential in renewable energy applications, particularly in solar and wind power conversion systems [8,9]. MLIs are especially well-suited for medium-voltage and high-power applications [10,11]. One of the key features of MLIs is their ability to produce a high output voltage in a staircase waveform using multiple DC input sources [12].

This stepped waveform closely resembles a pure sine wave, which helps reduce total harmonic distortion (THD) [13–15]. As a result, the reliance on bulky filters can be minimized [16]. Additionally, the staircase output reduces the rate of voltage change (dv/dt), which lowers stress on the load and improves system reliability [17]. Since the total voltage across each

switch is relatively low, MLIs can utilize switches with lower voltage ratings, making the overall design more cost-effective [18]. Another benefit of MLIs is the availability of multiple switching combinations to generate the same voltage level. This redundancy allows for fault-tolerant operation, enhancing system robustness [19].

Conventional MLI topologies include the Neutral-Point Clamped (NPC), Flying Capacitor (FC), and Cascaded H-Bridge (CHB) structures, introduced in 1981, 1990, and 1996, respectively [20–22]. While these designs offer improvements over traditional two-level inverters, they come with certain drawbacks, such as the need for a large number of switches, capacitors, or DC voltage sources [23]. To address these limitations, researchers have developed newer MLI topologies that use fewer components while maintaining or improving efficiency. These modern configurations are generally categorized into two types based on the voltage levels of their DC sources: symmetrical, where all sources are equal, and asymmetrical, where source magnitudes differ [11]. Several modulation strategies have been explored in the literature [14,15].

Many MLI designs incorporate an H-bridge circuit to generate both positive and negative output voltage levels [22]. In some topologies, the number of DC sources may exceed the number of switches used, highlighting the diversity in design approaches [23]. In this paper, a symmetrical 15-level MLI topology is proposed. The performance of the developed configuration is evaluated using MATLAB/Simulink simulations under RL load conditions at a modulation index of 1. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 3 describes the operational principle and modulation technique of the proposed inverter; Section 4 outlines the various operating modes; and Section 5 presents the simulation parameters along with the obtained results and their analysis.

II. PROPOSED CIRCUIT TOPOLOGY

This section discusses the proposed circuit topology. Fig.1 illustrates the proposed symmetric 15-level MLI topology, which is systematically organized into a level synthesis unit and a polarity reversal unit to streamline control and maintain hardware efficiency. The configuration employs twelve power switches, including five bidirectional switches (T_8 through T_{12}) that enable current conduction in both directions, while the remaining unidirectional switches manage voltage insertion and polarity conversion.

Operating in a symmetric mode with equal DC voltage sources, the topology ensures uniform voltage sharing and minimizes imbalance issues. By selectively inserting or bypassing these sources through strategic switch combinations, multiple stepped voltage levels are generated at the DC-link stage. The full-bridge polarity unit then converts this stepped DC into a complete AC output with both positive and negative half-cycles, achieving fifteen distinct voltage levels including zero. This symmetric design offers reduced component count, enhanced harmonic performance, balanced device stress, and practical suitability for medium-voltage and renewable energy applications.

Fig. 1. Proposed 15-level topology

III. MODULATION AND CONTROL OF MLI

Several modulation techniques such as PWM, SHE, nearest level control, and SVPWM are used to improve the efficiency and waveform quality of multilevel inverters. In this study, sinusoidal PWM (SPWM) is applied to generate switching signals for a 15-level inverter. A sinusoidal reference signal is compared with fourteen high-frequency triangular carrier waves arranged in different bands. The continuous comparison using fourteen comparators produces switching pulses, which are combined to form the inverter switching pattern. These signals generate the stepped output waveform and are further decoded to obtain the required gate pulses for the power semiconductor devices. In Fig. 2(a), several high-frequency triangular carrier waves are compared with a low-frequency sinusoidal reference waveform to generate the switching signals. Fig. 2(b) shows the resulting stepped output voltage waveform produced through this switching operation.

Fig. 2: Carrier-based PWM scheme: (a) Interaction of carrier signals with the reference waveform; (b) Corresponding switching pattern of the 15-MLI.

IV. MODES OF OPERATION

The various voltage generation modes of the 15-level MLI are depicted in Fig. 3. In the proposed topology, the current path during the positive half-cycle is indicated by the green arrow, whereas the current path for the negative half-cycle is shown by the red arrow. For the maximum positive level, +7Vdc, switches S1, S2, S6, and S7 are ON, while +6Vdc is obtained using S1, S2, S5, and S6. The +5Vdc level is produced by activating S1, S2, S7, and

S8. The intermediate positive levels are generated as follows: +4Vdc with S2 and S9, +3Vdc with S2 and S10, +2Vdc with S2 and S11, and +1Vdc with S2 and S12. The zero-voltage level (0Vdc) is achieved by turning ON S2 and S4. For the negative half-cycle, -1Vdc is generated with S3, S7, S8, and S9 ON; -2Vdc with S3, S7, S8, and S10; -3Vdc with S3, S7, S8, and S11; -4Vdc with S3, S7, S8, and S10; -5Vdc with S3, S4, S7, and S8; -6Vdc with S3, S4, S5, and S6; and -7Vdc with S3, S4, S6, and S7. In this manner, all fifteen voltage levels are produced through distinct switching combinations, enabling proper connection of the DC sources to synthesize the desired stepped output waveform.

Fig.4. Modes of operation of the proposed 15-level MLI

V. SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The model of the proposed 15-level MLI is developed and simulated in MATLAB/Simulink R2019b environment to investigate its electrical performance under defined operating conditions. To enable symmetrical operation, the DC source magnitudes are selected as $V_1 = 40\text{ V}$, $V_2 = 40\text{ V}$, $V_3 = 40\text{ V}$, $V_4 = 40\text{ V}$, $V_5 = 40\text{ V}$, $V_6 = 40\text{ V}$ and $V_7 = 40\text{ V}$. This uniform voltage distribution increases the number of output voltage steps, resulting in 15 distinct levels. The inverter performance is studied at modulation indices of 1. At a modulation index of 1, the inverter feeding an RL load of $150\ \Omega$ resistance and 75 mH inductance produces a maximum output voltage of 280 V as depicted in Fig. 4(a) and a peak current of 1.85 A as depicted in Fig. 4(b). The reduced THD is primarily due to the higher number of voltage levels, which improves waveform approximation and makes the inverter suitable for practical power applications.

Fig. 4. Simulation results (a) output voltage; (b) load current,

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a symmetrical 15-level multilevel inverter (MLI) topology with a reduced switch count and improved output performance. The proposed configuration employs twelve switches, including five bidirectional switches, and is divided into a level synthesis unit and a polarity reversal (H-bridge) unit. The use of seven equal 40 V DC sources ensures balanced voltage sharing and simplified control. By selectively inserting the DC sources, the inverter successfully generates fifteen distinct voltage levels, resulting in improved waveform quality and reduced THD. Simulation results obtained from MATLAB/Simulink R2019b under RL load conditions ($150\ \Omega$, 75 mH) at a modulation index of 1 confirm proper operation, achieving a maximum output voltage of 280 V and a peak current of 1.85 A . Overall, the proposed 15-level MLI demonstrates enhanced harmonic performance and practical suitability for medium-voltage and renewable energy applications.

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